

A SHORT REVIEW OF CHITINASE ENZYMES IN TETRAPOD VERTEBRATES

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ABSTRACT

Chitin is the second most abundant biopolymer after cellulose; being so abundant in nature, there definitely has to be a natural process for its degradation unless it should bioaccumulate in nature, this natural mechanism of degradation of chitin is chitinolysis, and one of the major group of enzymes performing this lysis of chitin are the chitinases. As the name suggests chitinolysis is the process of lysis of the chitin fibre, chitinases in particular hydrolyse the glycosidic bonds in between the substituted glucose (N-Acetylglucosamine) units, thus these enzymes are glycohydrolases. Chitinases are widely distributed among living organisms from bacteria to mammals; this review is a summary of the chitinases and chitinolytic activity present in tetrapod vertebrates giving a few examples under each class of the superclass Tetrapoda i.e., Pisces, Amphibia, Reptilia, Aves and Mammalia.

Keywords: Chitin, chitinase, vertebrates, tetrapod.

INTRODUCTION

Chitinases catalyze the hydrolysis of chitin, an unbranched polymer of β -1,4-N-acetylglucosamine. chitinases can be broadly classified into – i) Endochitinases that randomly break down the complex chitin polymer into simpler tetramers, trimers and dimers; and ii) Exochitinases that release acetylglucosamine monomers and chitobioses (**Cohen-Kupiec et al., 1998**), Exochitinases are further subdivided into two categories on the basis of release of the product: chitobiosidase and N-Acetylglucosaminidase. Chitobiosidase cleaves alternate β -1,4 glycosyl linkage in chitin from the non-reducing end producing chitobiose, whereas, N-Acetylglucosaminidase cleaves β -1,4 glycosyl linkage in chitin from non-reducing end producing GlcNAc (Acetylglucosamine monomers) (**Dukariya et al., 2020**)

Fig 1- Classification of chitinases

Fig 2 – Action of endochitinase

Fig 3 – Action of exochitinase.

The chitinases are grouped into three families: 18, 19, and 20 (**Henrissat, 1991**). Both families 18 and 19 consist of endochitinases from a variety of different organisms, including viruses, bacteria, fungi, insect, and plants. However, family 19 mainly comprises plant chitinases. Family 20 includes *N*-acetylglucosaminidase and a similar enzyme, *N*-acetylhexosaminidase (**Patil et al., 2000**).

Exochitinases were found in some bacteria such as *Thermococcus chitonophagus*, *Microbispora sp* (a common plant symbiont), and *Bacillus sp*. (**Fu et al., 2014**)

Chitin is almost always found crosslinked to other structural components. In fungal walls, it is found covalently bonded to glucans, either directly, as in case of *Candida albicans*, or via peptide bridges. In insects and other invertebrates, the chitin in all cases is always associated with specific proteins, with both covalent and noncovalent bonds, to produce the observed ordered structures (**Goody, 1990**).

IN FISHES (PISCES)

Fish ingest chitinous substances through their diets mainly in the form of crustaceans and zooplankton, it has been found by HPLC analysis that Osteichthyes contain many chitinases with varying biochemistries (**Ikeda et al., 2017**).

In one study that analysed the chitinolytic activity in marine fishes it was found that chitinase (endochitinase) activity, as well as chitobiase (exochitinase) activity was present in the stomach and intestine tissue (higher in stomach tissue), while the chitinolytic activity of a shark species was found to be lower than the 13 teleosts' surveyed, the chitinolytic (chitinase) activity of mesopelagic myctophids was found to be greater than demersal species (**Gutowska et al., 2004**).

In one study three chitinase genes – fChia1, fChia2 and fChia3 were isolated from the Japanese flounder, the fChia1 and fChia2 were found to be expressed in the stomach cells and produce an enzyme with acidic chitinase like activity, while fChia3 showed chitotriosidase like expression (**Kurokawa et al., 2004**).

Several studies have found that high chitinase activity also occurs in the blood plasma and lymphomyeloid tissues (except the thymus) of several Chondrichthyes and teleosts suggesting a defensive role against pathogens (**Fänge et al., 1976**).

In one study endogenous chitin was found to be present in the gut tissue, epithelial cells and scales of several fishes and certain cells in the appendages of certain salamanders (**Tang et al., 2015**).

The gut microbiota of fish is classified as autochthonous or indigenous when they can adhere and colonize the host's gut epithelial surface or allochthonous, when they are incidental visitors in the GI tract and are rejected after some time without colonizing. However, one study has hinted that the allochthonous microbiota might be able to 'colonize' the area between the villi during conditions like stress (**Ray et al., 2012**)

Bacillus chitinovor was one of the first chitin degrading bacteria isolated from the polluted waters of Kiel harbour (**Benecke., 1905**). A study with grey mullet reported that bacteria belonging to the genera Enterobacter, Vibrio and Pseudomonas had the capacity to degrade chitin (**Hamid et al.,1979**), all the studies assessing gut microbiota found chitinolytic bacteria in the gut of fishes.

IN AMPHIBIANS (AMPHIBIA)

A chitinolytic enzyme Toad Gastric Chitinase (tGCCase) was identified and described by (**Suzuki et al., 2001**) another enzyme called Toad Pancreatic Chitinase (tPCCase) with optimum pH of 6, was identified exclusively in the pancreas of a toad species (**Oshima et al., 2002**).

The enzyme was not found in the stomach of larvae, but was detected at stage 62 of metamorphosis and later, when the frogs changed from a herbivorous to a carnivorous diet (**Fujimoto et al., 2002**).

Some bacterial isolates from the skin of amphibians have shown chitinolytic activity and defense against Chytridiomycosis an amphibian skin disease caused by *Batrachochytrium dendrobatidis* (*Bd*) and *Batrachochytrium salamandrivorans* (A chytrid fungi), such metabolites are examples of exogenous enzymes (**Wax, 2021**).

IN REPTILES (REPTILIA)

A chitinase showing homology to the chitotriosidase (one of the major chitinases) in mammals was defined and isolated from the plasma of a few crocodilians, where it probably serves an immune function similar to chitotriosidase in mammals. The chitinase was found to show highest activity at physiological pH of 7 but was found showing lower activity at extreme pH (**Siroski et al., 2014**).

Insectivorous lizards and turtles secrete chitinase and chitobiase enzymes which aid in the digestion of the exoskeletons of insects and arachnids (**Cloudsley-Thompson, 1999**). In one study chitinase activity was found in the stomach and intestinal tissue of an insectivorous lizard *Sceloporus undulatus* showing higher activity at Ph 4.5 than at pH 7.5, chitinolytic activity was also found in the pancreatic tissue extract (**Marsh et al., 2001**)

IN BIRDS (AVES)

Many birds rely on arthropods (like insects and crustaceans) as a food source. Up to 60% of arthropod dry mass can be cuticle and up to 30% can be chitin, however the digestibility of chitin might differ among the avian species – for example in one study it was found to be about 10% in American robins and Bobwhites who have a diet consisting mainly of crickets and other such insects (Weiser et al., 1997) while another study showed a significantly higher chitin digestibility of about 39-85% by several species of seabirds (Jackson et al., 1992), the authors speculate this may be due to the richer gut microbiota in sea birds compared to other birds and also due to the self-digesting chitinase activity of certain marine crustaceans like krill. (Kehrt, 2020)

IN MAMMALS (MAMMALIA)

Mammalian chitinases belong to the family 18 of glycosyl hydrolases (GH18), which can be divided into chitinase like proteins with no enzymatic activity, and enzymatically active true chitinases. Chitotriosidase was the first mammalian (human) chitinase to be identified (Hamid et al., 2013) .

Another type of chitinase found in mammalian systems is the acidic mammalian chitinase (AMCase) that degrades chitin fibres releasing dimers of glucosamine (GlcNAc) (Ohno et al., 2016.), compared to the chitotriose released by chitotriosidase (by breakdown of chitotriose)

Both chitotriose and acidic mammalian chitinases have been seen to be produced by certain immune cells in mammals, suggesting an immune function against chitin containing pathogens (Kanneganti et al., 2012)

Some studies have suggested the hypothesis that susceptibility to parasitic infections like malaria has helped in the maintenance of the CHIT1 allele responsible for chitotriosidase production (Rosa et al., 2022.)

In contrast to chitotriosidase, the enzyme AMCase is extremely acid stable and shows a distinct second pH optimum around pH 2 (thus suggesting a higher activity in the acidic environment of the mammalian stomach) (Boot et al., 2001).

In one study the gastrointestinal tracts of seven insectivorous bat species (*Pipistrellus pipistrellus*, *Plecotus auritus*, *Myotis bechsteinii*, *Myotis nattereri*, *Myotis daubentonii*, *Myotis myotis*, and *Nyctalus leisleri*) were tested for chitinolytic activity by diffusion assay. Gastrointestinal tracts of *P. pipistrellus*, *P. auritus*, *M. nattereri*, *M. myotis*, and *N. leisleri* were examined for acidic mammalian chitinase by western blot

analysis and the chitinolytic activity was analysed by preparing agar gel Petri plates saturated with a chitin solution and testing extracts from the various parts of the GI tract and as expected the stomach extract showed quite high chitinolytic activity (greatest at an acidic pH between 5 and 6) (**Strobel et al., 2013**).

Bats however have a shorter intestinal tract compared to mammals of similar size, and thus a different microbiota with different adaptations (**Galey, 2020**), it is hypothesised that one of these features is the production of chitinase, which helps in the lysis of chitin in their insectivorous diets. One study showed chitinolytic bacteria in Sunda pangolins, including *Lactococcus*, *Bacteroides*, *Bacillus* and *Staphylococcus* (**Zhang et al., 2021**), indicating that specialised myrmecophagid and insectivorous mammals contain gut microbiota that supplement the endogenous chitinolytic activity in the gut.

Chitotriosidase thought to be an exochitinase hydrolyses colloidal chitin and releases chitobiose (**Fusetti et al., 2002**), although the enzyme was initially thought to be an exochitinase because it can hydrolyze chitotriose residues and was termed chitotriosidase based on this observation. However, recent structural and binding modes studies revealed the enzyme to be more of an endochitinase rather than an exochitinase (**Elmonem et al., 2016**)

In one study of the crab eating monkey (*Macaca fascicularis*) levels of AMCase and CHIT1 messenger RNAs (mRNAs) were highest in the stomach and the lung, respectively, leading again to the hypothesis that AMCases have a more active role in hydrolysis of chitin in the diet, while Chitotriosidases a more active role in immunity (**Uehara et al., 2018**)

An interesting product related to chitin processing in mammals is the Ambergris in sperm whales, chitinous material like squid pens and beaks which are a large part of the sperm whales' diet are regularly vomited out, but rarely pass through the intestine and get deposited in the rectum, where the coprolitic structure until eventually the rectum breaks and the Ambergris floats out (**Clarke, R., 2006**)

SOME KNOWN APPLICATIONS.

One of the first and logical applications of chitinases would be as pesticides to control insect and nematode pests, since chitin is a part of the shells, exoskeletons, and gut linings of arthropods (crustaceans and insects) , and makes up the structural frameworks of certain Protista as well as of nematode eggs (**Veliz et al., 2017**), however since extraction of the enzyme from invertebrates and even more so from vertebrates is a costly and complicated affair, thus microorganisms producing endogenous chitinases are used for biocontrol of such pests.

Another application of chitinase is as an antibacterial (Medeiros et al., 2018) and antifungal (Selitrennikoff, 2001) agent, since murein in bacterial cell walls can be considered a structural chitin homologue, as it is composed of alternating (1→4)-β-linked GlcNAc and N-acetylmuramic acid units (Beier & Bertilsson, 2013) and chitin is an essential structural component of the fungal cell wall (Bowman & Free, 2006).

Chitinases are also used in the agriculture industry to produce fertilizer since they can break down chitin fibres and make the carbon and nitrogen in chitin more bioavailable (Hamid et al., 2013)

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

Chitinases are present in all tetrapod vertebrates, even the ones that do not produce chitin themselves like mammals which were earlier believed not to produce chitinase but later several chitinases were identified in mammals. Mammalian chitinases were described as endochitinases of family 18 glycohydrolases even though some exochitinase activity was observed. A quick short review clarifies that the main functions of chitinase is immunity against chitinous parasites/pathogens and digestion of ingested chitin in the diet.

Chitinases can be endogenous enzymes produced by the organism itself or exogenous enzymes produced by other organisms like symbiotic bacteria living in the host organism. It has been found that the exogenous chitinases complement the endogenous chitinases in producing the chitinolytic activity.

Organisms that have microbiota producing chitinases supplementing the endogenous chitinases produced by that organism, showed greater chitinolytic activity.

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